

1 **Hnf4a functions in organ-specific TRA induction.**

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7 We discovered a novel organ-specific TRA regulatory control function for Hnf4a based on our discovery of
8 TRA presentation as a means of immune surveillance evasion. We distinguished this function from a
9 general TRA function (e.g., AIRE) and from liver- organogenesis specific functions of other Hnf-related
10 factors.

11 Citations

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